

Ethical and legal model for training Uzbekistan's athletes

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Abstract

This article systematically analyzes the legal nature of conflict situations arising from athletes' participation in international sports competitions, the factors that cause them, and the international legal mechanisms used to resolve these disputes. The article also examines the main sources of international sports law, the practice of sports arbitration, the regulations of sports federations, and the effectiveness of alternative dispute resolution mechanisms.

Keywords: international sports law, sports disputes, arbitration, disciplinary liability, legal mechanism, athlete rights.

Introduction

In today's context of globalization and the growing prestige of sports in the international arena, athletes' participation in international competitions is directly related not only to sports results but also to their moral culture and legal literacy. Strict rules established by international sports organizations (IOC, international federations, WADA, etc.) demand a high level of moral responsibility and legal discipline from athletes.

From this point of view, the absence of a unified model that systematically, consistently, and integrally integrates ethical and legal requirements in the process of preparing Uzbekistan's athletes for international competitions is emerging as a practical and theoretical problem. In most cases, athletes, while paying sufficient attention to technical-tactical and physical training, are entering the field without adequate preparation for issues such as legal restrictions, disciplinary penalties, ethical conflicts, and doping-related responsibilities encountered in international competitions.

The moral and legal model for preparing Uzbekistan's athletes for international competitions consists of the following parts:

Normative-legal part - a set of systemic documents containing legal norms, rules, and requirements in the field of sports.

Unified National Requirements Standard - a system of unified national requirements and criteria for admitting athletes to competitions.

Regulations for the Protection of Young Athletes - a set of rules aimed at ensuring the rights, health, and safety of young athletes.

"Athlete-age" status - the official status of an athlete who belongs to the youth category according to their age, level of training, and legal status.

Harmonization with the WADA Code - the process of adapting the requirements of the World Anti-Doping Agency Code to national sports legislation and practice.

The moral-psychological component - a system aimed at ensuring moral norms and psychological stability in sports activities.

- Sports Code of Ethics - a set of rules that establish behavioral norms for athletes, coaches, and officials.

- Monitoring coaches' ethics - a mechanism for monitoring and evaluating the adherence to ethical principles in coaches' activities.

- Psychological support - measures aimed at strengthening athletes' mental state and alleviating stress and competitive pressure.

Educational component - an educational system that serves to develop knowledge and competencies in the field of sports.

- "Sports Law and Ethics" course - a subject aimed at teaching sports legislation, international standards, and ethical principles.

- Coach support - ensuring coaches' professional activities, psychological stability, and methodological preparation.

- Professional development - the process of regularly updating knowledge, skills, and professional expertise of specialists in the sports field.

The ethical and legal model for training Uzbekistan's athletes consists of the following components:

- Legal component - a system encompassing legal norms, requirements, and rules in the field of sports.

- Unified requirement standards - a set of unified legal requirements and standards applied when admitting athletes to competitions.

- Protection of young athletes - legal safeguarding of young athletes' rights, health, and safety.

- Anti-doping prevention - legal, organizational, and promotional measures aimed at preventing violations of doping rules.

Ethical component - a system aimed at ensuring ethical principles and values in the field of sports.

- Code of Ethics - a set of rules that establish behavioral norms for participants in sports activities.

- Coaching ethics - norms of moral responsibility, fairness, and pedagogical etiquette in a coach's professional activity.

- Psychological support - measures aimed at ensuring the mental stability of athletes and helping them overcome stressful situations.

Educational component - an educational system aimed at developing knowledge, skills, and competencies in the field of sports.

- Training courses and professional development in sports law are educational processes aimed at improving sports legislation, practical training, and enhancing the professional capacity of specialists.

Organizational component - a system that ensures management, coordination, and institutional activities in the field of sports.

- The National Center for Sports Law is an institution that provides legal consultation, analysis, and expert services in the field of sports.

- Digital platforms - tools for organizing legal information, monitoring, and management processes in sports activities on a digital basis.

- Team lawyers - specialists who provide legal support for the activities of sports teams.

In conclusion, the legal mechanisms for resolving disputes involving our athletes in international sports competitions constitute a complex and multi-tiered system. The research results demonstrated that these mechanisms serve as a crucial instrument in safeguarding the rights and interests of athletes.

Achieving results in sports is a multifaceted and complex process. Success in high-performance sports is formed at the intersection of various conditions that influence an athlete's activities. These conditions can be grouped into several key interconnected aspects: organizational, legal, psychological,

medical, and methodological.

Organizational factors include the structure and quality of the athlete training system, and the effectiveness of sports programs and competition management. These encompass the availability of developed sports infrastructure (sports facilities, halls, equipment), a system for selecting and supporting talented athletes, financing and sponsorship, as well as the activities of sports federations and governing bodies.

From the standpoint of moral standards, the organizational culture within a team or national team is of particular importance. If the values of "clean sport," fair competition, and absolute intolerance towards doping are established at the management level, athletes will also feel the responsibility to adhere to these principles.

Organizational measures also include internal control mechanisms: implementation of collective codes of conduct, verification of the professional reputation of involved specialists, and monitoring of training loads and recovery methods.

Result and discussion

The establishment of the Ethics Commission under the National Anti-Doping Agency and the National Olympic Committee as an organizational resource in Uzbekistan has been of great importance. These structures are operating effectively at the national level by ensuring compliance with international standards, conducting educational activities, and coordinating oversight.

Thus, a well-designed organization of the sports sphere creates a solid foundation for the development of athletes without resorting to prohibited methods.

Legal support of sports is a set of laws, rules, and regulatory documents that define the activities of athletes and coaches, as well as the procedure for participating in competitions. These include international documents (Olympic Charter, World Anti-Doping Code, UNESCO conventions) and national legislation (laws on physical education and sports, orders of the Ministry of Sports, anti-doping rules of national federations).

A clear and comprehensive legal framework establishes the "rules of the game" that are mandatory for everyone. In recent years, legal norms have been continuously improved: new regulations are being introduced to close loopholes for violators, and

Table 1. Knowledge and skills to be acquired within the program for developing athletes' knowledge and skills on ethical and legal rules

N	Knowledge and skills to be acquired	N	Knowledge and skills to be acquired
1.	The Concept of Ethics and Law in Sport	6.	Anti-doping rules and responsibility
2.	Sports ethics and fair play principle	7.	Disputed situations in competitions
3.	Athlete's ethical responsibility	8.	Stress, aggression, and conflicts
4.	Sports legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan	9.	Athlete's Code of Conduct
5.	International sports law and federation rules		

accountability is being strengthened.

In particular, the World Anti-Doping Code adopted in 2021 tightened sanctions for certain violations and placed greater emphasis on the athlete's environmental responsibility. Uzbekistan ratified UNESCO's International Convention against Doping in Sport and integrated its provisions into the national legal system.

The country has developed national anti-doping rules that comply with WADA requirements, which has been confirmed by a positive assessment from WADA.

The legal factor also encompasses athletes' contractual obligations: contracts concluded with national team and club members stipulate conditions for strict adherence to anti-doping rules and behavioral norms, violation of which leads to contract termination and financial penalties.

Thus, the effectiveness of the legal factor is manifested in the inevitability of punishment for violations and in encouraging athletes to act within the framework of the law.

An athlete's psychological preparation has two dimensions:

- firstly, developing competitive resilience, motivation, ability to overcome stress, and capacity to focus attention on goals;
- secondly, forming moral beliefs and values that prevent deviation from the path of integrity.

Great athletes achieve victory not only due to their physical capabilities but also due to their strong character and principles. An athlete who has developed the belief from a young age that "victory is valuable only when achieved honestly" will not resort to rule-breaking even in conditions of fierce competition.

The psychological atmosphere in the team is also of great importance: the coach's support, trusting relationships, and the absence of pressure to "win at all costs" create a healthy environment. Practical psychological methods include discussions on the topic of ethics, meetings with famous athletes who have achieved success without doping, and motivational training.

The psychologist must constantly monitor the athlete's condition and eliminate destructive states such as fear and lack of self-confidence. As a result, the psychological factor strengthens the athlete's willpower and ensures their loyalty to the honor of sports.

In modern sports, medical and biological support is an integral component. This includes proper nutrition, the use of permitted supplements, recovery monitoring, injury prevention and treatment, and physiotherapy services.

One of the main medical factors is anti-doping support. Team doctors must check the composition of all medications and supplements taken by the athlete and regularly monitor updates to the WADA list of prohibited substances.

The role of sports physicians is to explain the negative consequences of doping and propose methods to enhance performance within legal boundaries. For instance, recommending balanced nutrition instead of anabolic steroids, and proper sleep and rest regimens instead of stimulants.

Additionally, conducting regular internal doping tests within teams can prevent negative situations in international competitions. A healthy athlete can maintain consistent performance over an extended period.

Based on the analyses conducted, several

conclusions can be drawn about the initial effectiveness of the model aimed at improving legal and ethical guidelines to ensure athletes' participation in international competitions.

The model encompasses a comprehensive set of measures including educational initiatives, organizational and legal mechanisms, psychological preparation, medical support, and training methodologies.

Preliminary results indicate positive outcomes. Foremost, athletes' awareness and sense of responsibility have increased. Following anti-doping seminars, athletes began paying serious attention to the composition of supplements they consume. This signifies an increase in "anti-doping culture."

Coaches have also started to place greater emphasis on preventive measures. Some teams have introduced designated ethics and anti-doping officials. This has enhanced collective responsibility.

Psychological training has reduced stress in athletes, and a healthy motivation is forming to replace the notion that "victory should be achieved by any means."

Individual recovery programs were developed in the medical unit, and not a single doping violation was recorded among the program participants, which is considered the most crucial indicator.

Due to organizational and legal measures, sports schools and clubs are being provided with timely updated information. This serves to prevent violations.

At the same time, work must continue uninterrupted. It is necessary to regularly update educational programs and monitor their effectiveness.

Overall, the model is showing its effectiveness in a short period: knowledge has increased, attitudes have changed, and no violations have been recorded. This approach demonstrates its ability to lead athletes towards fair and sustainable victories.

Achieving high results in the modern sports system is inextricably linked not only to the level of physical and technical preparedness but also to the moral consciousness, legal culture, and social responsibility of athletes. International sports practice shows that disciplinary violations, doping cases, and actions contrary to sports ethics arising during competitions indicate insufficient formation of moral and legal knowledge and skills among athletes. From this perspective, developing a special program aimed at enhancing athletes'

knowledge and skills in ethical and legal rules, and scientifically and theoretically substantiating its effectiveness, is of current scientific and practical significance.

From a scientific and theoretical perspective, the effectiveness of this program is primarily explained by the theory of personality socialization. According to this theory, an individual's personality is shaped through the internalization of norms, rules, and values present in a specific social environment. The sports environment represents a unique social space where moral norms (fair competition, respect for opponents, integrity) and legal rules (competition regulations, requirements of international federations, disciplinary accountability) define the consistent behavior of an athlete's personality. This program serves to systematically, purposefully, and consistently assimilate these norms, which ensures its theoretical effectiveness.

Secondly, the program's effectiveness is also grounded in a competency-based approach. According to this approach, the ability to apply knowledge in practice takes precedence over the mere possession of knowledge. Moral and legal competence in athletes encompasses the ability to know the rules, understand them, evaluate them, and make appropriate decisions in various sporting situations. The program integrates theoretical knowledge with practical exercises, case analyses, and situational tasks, which contributes to the development of stable skills in athletes. This scientifically substantiates the pedagogical effectiveness of the program.

Thirdly, this program is based on an axiological approach. The axiological approach aims to form a system of values in an individual, and in the field of sports, it encompasses values such as honesty, responsibility, law-abidingness, patriotism, and humanitarianism. Teaching moral and legal rules is not limited to merely providing information but leads athletes to understand the personal significance of these rules. Moral and legal norms, when accepted as values, consistently regulate an athlete's behavior, which is considered an important theoretical criterion for the program's effectiveness.

Fourthly, the effectiveness of the program is also substantiated from the perspective of a systemic-activity approach. Moral and legal education is effective when implemented not through isolated episodic activities, but through continuous, systematic, and purposeful action.

In the program, goals, objectives, content, forms, methods, and results are expressed in a logically interconnected manner, ensuring its internal systemic integrity. As a result, moral and legal knowledge in athletes does not remain merely at an informational level but transforms into skills and abilities that manifest in practical activities.

Fifthly, the effectiveness of this program is explained by its preventive and educational influence mechanism. An athlete possessing moral and legal knowledge anticipates the legal consequences of their actions and consciously restrains behaviors that contradict moral norms. This serves to prevent disciplinary violations, situations contrary to sports ethics, and potential conflicts that may arise during international competitions. Thus, the program holds not only educational but also preventive significance, thereby increasing its socio-pedagogical effectiveness.

In the current context of globalization, not only the physical and technical preparation of athletes but also their moral and legal culture is of great importance. Specifically, one of the urgent tasks is the systematic organization of training sessions aimed at developing knowledge and skills in moral and legal rules to ensure the worthy participation of Uzbek athletes in international sports arenas. Such training sessions serve to reinforce qualities like honesty, fairness, discipline, responsibility, and respect for the law among athletes.

Training sessions for the development of moral and legal knowledge should be planned as an integral part of the sports training process. These sessions should be organized through a combination of theoretical and practical training, aiming to familiarize athletes with international and national sports law norms, sports ethics, anti-doping rules, behavioral standards in competitions, and sports discipline. It is particularly important to thoroughly study the content of the Olympic Charter, regulations of international sports federations, and the legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan related to sports.

The use of interactive pedagogical methods in organizing these sessions enhances their effectiveness. Specifically, analyzing problematic situations, conducting case studies based on legal and ethical scenarios from real sports practices, engaging in discussions, role-playing, and training exercises develop athletes' skills in independent thinking and responsible

decision-making. This approach serves to prevent athletes from committing offenses and ethical violations during competitions.

Additionally, the collaboration of coaches, sports psychologists, and sports law specialists is crucial for the effective organization of moral and legal training. The personal example set by coaches and their fair and lawful treatment of athletes serve as an important educational factor in shaping the moral and legal consciousness of athletes. In this regard, it is advisable to apply a differentiated approach, taking into account the age and level of preparation of the athletes.

Experimental work aimed at developing the knowledge of Uzbekistan's athletes on ethical and legal rules was carried out within the framework of the "Sports Law" course. This course is taught to student-athletes studying in the sports activity education program at the Uzbekistan State University of Physical Education and Sports, its Nukus branch, as well as during the coaching professional development courses at the Institute for Retraining and Advanced Training of Physical Education and Sports Specialists.

The work on improving the knowledge of student-athletes and participants of the coaching professional development courses was carried out within the framework of the Program for Developing Athletes' Knowledge and Skills in Ethical and Legal Rules.

In the modern sports system, an athlete's performance is determined not only by physical and technical training but also by high moral standards and legal awareness. Systematic acquisition of knowledge such as "The Concept of Ethics and Law in Sport," "Sports Ethics and the Fair Play Principle," "Ethical Responsibility of an Athlete," "Sports Legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan," "International Sports Law and Federation Rules," "Anti-Doping Rules and Responsibility," "Disputed Situations in Competitions," "Stress, Aggression, and Conflicts," and "Athlete's Code of Conduct" ensures a qualitatively new stage in athletes' preparation (see Table 2).

We organized experimental work based on the knowledge and skills that should be acquired within the Program for Developing Athletes' Knowledge and Skills on Ethical and Legal Rules.

At the initial stage of the study, 50 student-athletes studying in the field of sports activities at the Uzbekistan State University of Physical Education and Sport participated. The results

Table 2. Indicators of knowledge and skill development regarding moral and legal rules in the experimental group subjects. (UzSUWL, Nukus Branch, Institute for Retraining and Advanced Training of Specialists in Physical Education and Sports)

Research Organizations where the study was conducted		Beginning of the experiment			End of experiment			AAD	RG	t	P
		X	σ	V, %	X	σ	V, %				
UzSUWL (n=50)	CG	5.80	0.85	14.60	6.16	0.9	14.61	0.36	6.18	2.05	<0.05
	EG	5.83	0.87	14.97	6.54	0.92	14.14	0.71	12.17	3.95	<0.001
Nukus branch (n=30)	CG	5.74	0.78	13.60	6.19	0.77	12.44	0.45	7.76	2.22	<0.05
	EG	5.75	0.80	13.92	6.44	0.85	13.13	0.70	12.12	3.28	<0.01
IAT (n=30)	CG	5.73	0.72	12.64	6.13	0.77	12.48	0.40	7.03	2.09	<0.05
	EG	5.72	0.74	12.94	6.40	0.78	12.11	0.68	11.93	3.49	<0.01

showed the development of knowledge and skills among the student-athletes.

Additionally, at the second stage of the study, 30 student-athletes studying in the field of sports activities at the Nukus branch of the Uzbekistan State University of Physical Education and Sport took part. The results demonstrated the development of knowledge and skills among these student-athletes as well.

In the final stage of the study, 30 participants from the advanced training courses for sports coaches at the Institute for Retraining and Advanced Training of Specialists in Physical Education and Sports took part. The results indicated that the trainees' knowledge and skills had improved.

Results of the conducted research The study demonstrated the development of knowledge and skills among student-athletes studying in the field of sports activities at the Uzbekistan State University of Physical Education and Sport, student-athletes studying in the field of sports activities at the Nukus branch of the Uzbekistan State University of Physical Education and Sport, as well as trainees of the advanced training course for sports coaches at the Institute for Retraining and Advanced Training of Specialists in Physical Education and Sports (see Table 3).

The results of the conducted scientific and pedagogical research confirm the effectiveness of targeted educational and upbringing work aimed at developing the knowledge and skills of Uzbek athletes in moral and legal rules. The study showed that the knowledge and skills of student-athletes studying in the field of sports activities at the Uzbekistan State University of Physical Education and Sports increased by 12.17%, those of student-athletes studying in the same field at the Nukus branch of the

Uzbekistan State University of Physical Education and Sports increased by 12.12%, and the knowledge and skills of participants in the advanced training course for sports coaches at the Institute for Retraining and Advanced Training of Physical Education and Sports Specialists increased by 11.93% (see Table 4.15).

Diagnostic analysis conducted at the initial stage of the study revealed varying levels of knowledge among student-athletes and coaches regarding ethical and legal rules, particularly in sports ethics, fair play principles, international sports law, and anti-doping requirements. Notably, student-athletes showed insufficient systematization of theoretical knowledge and incomplete understanding of how to apply legal norms in practical sports activities. Simultaneously, while trainees in the coaches' advanced training course demonstrated relatively higher knowledge in this area, there was an identified need for specific methodological approaches to effectively apply this knowledge in athlete education.

The moral and legal education model developed and implemented during the research process, along with special classes, seminar-trainings, situational tasks, tests, and methodological tools based on problem situation analysis, led to positive changes in participants' knowledge, skills, and attitudes. The experiment results showed that student-athletes at the Uzbekistan State University of Physical Education and Sports and its Nukus branch significantly improved their understanding of organizing sports activities based on legal and ethical norms. Furthermore, their behavior, sense of responsibility, and discipline during competitions underwent positive changes.

In particular, student-athletes gained a clearer understanding of anti-doping rules, athletes' rights and obligations, and norms of behavior in international competitions. They began to consciously establish legal and ethical boundaries in their activities. This served to reduce the likelihood of errors and rule violations in their sports activities.

Conclusion

Significant progress was also noted among the participants of the coaches' professional development course. They gained a deeper understanding that moral and legal education is a factor directly affecting sports results, and acknowledged the necessity of a preventive approach, explanatory talks, and educational conversations when working with athletes. During the study, it was observed that coaches increased their focus on integrating moral and legal issues into the training process and paid more attention to individual work with athletes.

Overall, the research results show that developing the knowledge and skills of Uzbekistan's athletes and sports specialists regarding ethical and legal rules is highly effective when organized on the basis of a systematic, continuous, and comprehensive approach. Educational and upbringing work in this direction serves not only to help athletes achieve high results but also to shape them as individuals who defend the country's honor and sports reputation in the international arena, committed to the norms of law and morality.

Thus, the results obtained within the framework of the study confirm the practical significance of the developed model and methodological recommendations and scientifically substantiate the expediency of their wide implementation in the sports education system of the republic, including in higher educational institutions, branches, and professional development courses for coaches.

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